

Healthy soils as a booster to EU competitiveness

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ABSTRACT

The European Union's strategic agenda for 2024–2029 prioritizes a prosperous and competitive Europe, with soil health potentially playing a role in achieving this goal. However, the current state of European soils is of concern, with over 60 % of soils not in healthy condition, as reported by the European Union's Soil Mission Board and the EU Soil Observatory. This results not only in environmental issues, but also economic ones, as the costs of soil degradation in the EU are estimated to be higher than €50 billion per year, underscoring the need for soil health to be placed more prominently on the political agenda. Soil-related business models, including biotechnology, remediation of contaminated sites, carbon removals and farming, regenerative agriculture, and agritech solutions, can contribute to EU competitiveness. These business models may help address most of the challenges posed by soil degradation, climate change, and biodiversity loss, while promoting sustainable agriculture practices and improving ecosystem functioning. The EU's soil remediation market is valued at €8.5 billion, with an annual growth rate of 5 %. The EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Regulation provides a framework for certifying carbon removals, with potential revenue of €6 billion per year. Regenerative agriculture, which prioritises soil health and ecosystem services, can increase crop yields, reduce dependency on synthetic fertilisers and pesticides, and promote biodiversity. Agritech solutions, such as precision agriculture and artificial intelligence, can optimize farming practices, reduce costs, and improve environmental sustainability. Here we present the potential of soil-related business models to contribute to EU competitiveness, while addressing environmental and societal challenges. However, a number of challenges remain and need to be addressed as the need for acceleration, a clear policy framework, a closer collaboration of different actors in the food supply chain and a digital transformation are still needed.

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1. Background

The European Union’s (EU) strategic agenda for 2024–2029 has set out three priority areas, reaching "A Prosperous and Competitive Europe" being one of them (European Commission, 2024a). According to the glossary of the EU’s law portal, the term “competitiveness” relates to the definition “A competitive economy is an economy whose sustained rate of productivity is able to drive growth and, consequently, income and welfare. Economic competitiveness has long been one of the key political priorities of the European Union (EU)” (EUR-lex, 2024).

In the State of the European Union Speech of 2023, President von der Leyen announced her request to Mario Draghi to prepare a report on the future of European competitiveness. In September 2024 “The future of European competitiveness – A competitiveness strategy for Europe” report (Draghi, 2024) was presented to the European Commission. The Draghi report lists the challenges faced by the industry and companies in the Single Market and warns Europe on the risk to no longer being able to rely on many of the factors that have supported growth in the past. The report lays out a clear diagnosis and provides concrete recommendations to put Europe onto a different trajectory. Following the Draghi report, in February 2025 the President of the European Commission presented the EU Compass to regain competitiveness stating: “Europe has everything it needs to succeed in the race to the top. But, at the same time, we must fix our weaknesses to regain competitiveness. The Competitiveness Compass transforms the excellent recommendations of the Draghi report into a roadmap”. The Competitiveness Compass identifies three core areas of action (Fig. 1): a) closing the innovation gap, b) a joint roadmap for decarbonisation and competitiveness, and c) reducing excessive dependencies and increasing security (European Commission, 2025a).

In its previous mandate (2019–2024), the European Commission emphasised the need to tackle climate change and environmental challenges by implementing a growth strategy to transform the EU into a fair and prosperous society with a resource-efficient and competitive economy (Montanarella and Panagos, 2021). The current strategic policy documents underscore the significance of climate and environmental objectives (European Commission, 2024a), due to their critical role in ensuring European economic security amidst a changing climate and advancing a resource-efficient transition of the European economy (European Commission, 2025a).

Economic security and a resource-efficient transition of the European economy require food security, water security, energy security, climate

change adaptation and mitigation, and the preservation of biodiversity and ecosystem services (Bouma and McBratney, 2013; McBratney et al., 2014). Soils play a key role in all these aspects, and their degradation is expected to lead to a significant decrease of security for people involved that, in turn, may affect social, economic and political security (Bouma and McBratney, 2013). It is estimated that around 60 % of EU soils are not in good condition (Panagos et al., 2024b). In addition, according to recent estimates, the economic cost of soil degradation in the EU is around €50 billion per year (European Commission, 2023). When disentangling the cost of soil degradation in relation to the different degradation processes, the value can range between €40.9 and 72.7 billion per year, reaching €140 billion if costs of soil biodiversity loss, floods, droughts, off-site effects of soil erosion, and health consequences of soil contamination are included (Panagos et al., 2025).

The state of the environment, and thereby healthy soils, is key for economic security and climate change adaptation as recognised in the EU Competitiveness Compass. Therefore, soils and the increased awareness of the importance of restoring their health and halt degradation, can give rise to novel business models. Business models are commonly defined as the conceptual architectures that specify how an organisation creates, delivers, and captures value within a given socio-technical context (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010). In later 1990’s and early 2000, the concept of soil health has focused largely on the soil productivity function (Acton and Gregorich, 1995; Kibblewhite et al., 2008). As a consequence, business models traditionally centre on the farmer’s capacity to transform land, labour, and inputs into food commodities that generate revenue streams. More recently, the concept of soil health has shifted from the emphasis on productivity towards the recognition of multi-functionality and variety of ecosystem services (ES) provided by soils (Bünemann et al., 2018). This growing recognition of soil health as a source of multiple ES -including carbon sequestration, water purification, flood buffering, and biodiversity support- demands a reframing of value creation beyond the farm gate. Soil functions deliver public and private benefits to a heterogeneous set of actors that operate both upstream and downstream of primary production.

In this contribution, we present and discuss a non-exhaustive set of examples on how soil-related business models increase EU competitiveness as highlighted by a recent event (12th June 2025), titled “How healthy soils contribute to EU competitiveness”, organised by the European Commission’s EU Soil Observatory in the frame of the 5th EUSO Stakeholders Forum.

Fig. 1. The three pillars of the Competitiveness Compass (top) and the examples of business models to increase competitiveness by improving soil health.

2. Examples on how healthy soils can contribute to EU competitiveness

In the framework of the EU Competitiveness Compass, soil-based business models (Fig. 1) can contribute to all three transformational imperatives to boost EU competitiveness, namely (1) integrating decarbonisation policies with industrial, competition, economic and trade policies (e.g. carbon farming, circular bioeconomy, regenerative agriculture and all players across the supply chain including banks and insurance), (2) commercially exploiting innovations to close the innovation gap (e.g. remediation, biotechnology and biodiversity, laboratories, biofertilizers and pesticides, circular bioeconomy, carbon farming and regenerative agriculture) and (3) Reducing excessive dependencies (e.g., replacing traditional chemical inputs for crop protection and synthetic fertilizers) to create a shift in farming practices with less reliance on synthetic inputs.

2.1. Biotechnology and soil biodiversity

Soil-living microorganisms naturally produce hundreds of chemical substances that allow them to interact with their surroundings. These molecules, which are a result of over 450 million years of evolution, may also act as powerful drugs. Indeed, it is well known that microbes are remarkable producers of substances that may improve human health and well-being (Ramírez-Rendon et al., 2022). As an example, rapamycin, first isolated in 1972 in soil samples from Easter Island (Rapa Nui), is a powerful immunosuppressant, with anti-cancer and anti-aging potential, largely used in hospitals worldwide.

The majority of naturally occurring antibiotics used in human and veterinary medicine have been derived from microorganisms that live in soil, including fungi and bacteria, particularly actinomycetes, which have proven to be a rich source for antibiotic production (Brevik et al., 2020). Indeed, several antibiotics were originally isolated by screening soil-derived actinomycetes during the golden era of antibiotic discovery in the 1940s to 1960s (Lewis, 2013). Actinobacteria remain the number one font of novel potential medical products (Gavriilidou et al., 2022). Other examples of microbial groups that can contribute to the exploration of new products include *Aspergillus*, *Cyanobacteria*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Burkholderia* (Fig. 2). Recently, scientists reported the identification and characterisation of a very promising new lasso peptide antibiotic (i. e., lariocidin) from a *Paenibacillus* isolated from soil (Jangra et al.,

2025). Such a discovery, once again, confirms the value of soil and its biodiversity for the development of much-needed antibacterial drugs.

Up until now, 500 approved drugs (e.g., anticancer, anti-infective, immunosuppressant) have been discovered by only scratching the surface of 3 % of microbial chemistry (Gavriilidou et al., 2022), thus confirming the biotechnological capacity of this research area. This potential is particularly relevant in a context of increasing antimicrobial resistance to commonly used medicines. According to the World Health Organization, antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is one of the top global public health and development threats. It is estimated that bacterial AMR was directly responsible for 1.27 million global deaths in 2019 and contributed to 4.95 million deaths (Murray et al., 2022). Thus, scientifically speaking, research to identify new products is much needed and, in economic terms, it could offer a competitive advantage to companies not just in the pharmaceutical but also agrochemicals (biopesticides) and cosmetics sectors. While extremely costly (median cost of getting a new drug into the market is \$985 million (Wouters et al., 2020)), drug development is valued in billions, with a new antibiotic that could lead to an average revenue of \$240 million annually (Blaskovich and Cooper, 2025).

In the EU, the Critical Medicines Act aims to improve the availability and security of essential medicines. In this context, looking at the EU Competitiveness Compass, the more effective and upscaling of identification of active pharmaceutical ingredients used for medicine production derived from soils would reduce EU dependencies and increase EU security (Fig. 1). Additionally, a technical challenge, to be tackled in the future, is the need to scale up a decentralized discovery engine that sources and investigates microbial diversity from diverse ecosystems across the continent, enabling the commercialisation of existing technologies to close the innovation gap and, thus, further promote EU competitiveness (Fig. 1).

2.2. Remediation of contaminated sites

The soil remediation market in the EU is valued around €8.5 billion with an increase of 5 % per year (Prasad et al., 2021). The EU’s Soil Monitoring Law and the EU Green Deal initiatives will likely accelerate market growth and commercialization of technologies (Fig. 1) by enforcing sustainable practices and remediation. Taking into account that there are 350,000 identified contaminated sites in the EU with a potential of 2.8 million sites (Panagos et al., 2013), the Soil Monitoring

Fig. 2. Example of microbial clades with strong biosynthetic potential. Most of these microbes can be found in the soil.

Law focus on their remediation. Integrating circular economy and bioeconomy principles into bioremediation techniques offers a cost-efficient approach to restore degraded ecosystems, while fostering a regenerative economy that rejuvenates natural resources and promotes environmental sustainability (Francocci et al., 2020). Around 8 % of EU lands are affected by high concentrations of heavy metals such as cadmium, mercury, zinc, copper and arsenic (Ballabio et al., 2024, 2018; Fendrich et al., 2024; Van Eynde et al., 2023).

Classical methods for removing the pollutants are based on biodegradation (e.g. hydrocarbons), chemical reactions (oxidation, reduction of heavy metals and halogenated compounds), thermal desorption, or other physical pathways like venting and multiphase extraction (solvents, gasoline) (Lim et al., 2016; Ossai et al., 2020). Microorganisms can be precious ally for bioremediation of diffuse pollution because of their metabolic and enzymatic activities (Abatenh et al., 2017), and in some extent, of more concentrated spillages. The microbial role in soil restoration also offers opportunities for the development of new biological products (i.e. closing the innovation gap, Fig. 1) that can accelerate bioremediation processes and/or the mobilisation of key nutrients as a component of the restoration process (Pande et al., 2020; Sible et al., 2021). Additionally, when sites or polluted areas have been remediated, the economic benefit may be, once again, exponential as the value of regenerated land would increase, making extensive areas available for additional investments (residential, energy, infrastructures). In recent years, companies performing remediation have been increasingly asked to create fertile soils by adding compost or natural organic matter (e.g., algae, food waste) and mixing it with the remediated soil. Restoring soil functions requires pedological engineering, which involves layering the soil with larger stones at the bottom and a mix of clay, silt, and organic matter at the top.

The remediation processes also allow, on the long term, for the restoration of soil organic carbon, even in urban environments, making it possible to support more plant life and contribute to the development of more resilient and sustainable cities, and, thus, contributing to decarbonisation.

2.3. Biodegradability in soils and circular bioeconomy

Bio-based products (e.g. crop residues) have a strong potential to be transformed in value-added products promoting sustainability (Lange et al., 2021), thereby reducing external dependencies (Fig. 1). In 2012, world consumption of plastics products in agriculture for plant and animal production amounts yearly to 6.5 million tons (Scarascia-Mugnozza et al., 2011) while this has doubled after a decade to 12.5 million tons (Briassoulis, 2023). This figure corresponding to 3–5 % of the total plastic production (FAO, 2021).

In Europe, the volume of plastic materials used in agriculture was approximately 1.8 million tons in 2018. Of those, films for agriculture represent approximately 722,000 tons with 1/3 used in Spain, Italy and France. The use of plastics in agriculture has partially improved agricultural practices, marking a shift in agricultural techniques, introducing innovative ways to enhance and improve crop production, optimize the use of resources and inputs (e.g.: fertilizers and phytosanitary products) and reduce the water demand. However, their use also comes with significant environmental, economic, and social costs primarily due to increased pollution. The quantity of agri-plastics entering the environment due to malpractice is unknown, as largely unknown are the quantities of plastics accumulating in the soil, as they are mainly dependent upon the different types of materials and their characteristics, use and end-of life management, local collection systems, infrastructure and legislation (Sa'adu and Farsang, 2023). When plastic material not properly collected and disposed, once in the environment it may fragment and remain there for many decades, resulting in soil pollution.

Residues of conventional agri-plastics in the soil can hinder water infiltration, decrease water-holding capacity, impact microbial

communities, reduce soil fertility, deteriorate soil health, and potentially contaminate the human food chain, posing a risk to human health (Hofmann et al., 2023). Certified soil biodegradable as well as certified compostable materials offer a solution to mitigate these costs by reducing waste and labour costs related to the proper end-of life management of agri-plastics. An example of application of biodegradable materials in agriculture are soil biodegradable mulch films. Thanks to their biodegradability in soil they eliminate the need for film removal contributing to saving farmers time and fuel. Unlike conventional plastic films, which can also lead to the removal of fertile soil (0.3 Million tons of topsoil per year in the EU, FAO, 2021), biodegradable mulch films contribute to soil fertility, making them a more sustainable alternative. Biodegradable mulch films proved to have positive effects on yields, earliness, product quality, weed control efficacy, microclimatic improvement for tomato crops, orchards (pepper, melon and other cucurbits, strawberry, lettuce) (Tofanelli and Wortman, 2020) and vineyards (Martín-Closas et al., 2017).

2.4. Carbon removals and carbon farming

The Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) regulation is the first EU framework for certifying carbon removals in a voluntary market, including those generated by carbon farming activities in agricultural mineral soils, peatland and forests (European Commission, 2024b). Cost-effective yet robust monitoring, reporting and verification systems, alongside reduced administrative costs, are generally perceived as important factors for a successful deployment of a voluntary carbon market (Criscuoli et al., 2024). On the other hand, the total revenue that could be generated at European level strongly depends on the potential of different ecosystems to store additional carbon or reduce their emissions.

According to latest LUCAS campaigns, the EU agricultural soils have lost around 0.75 % of their carbon during the period 2009–2018 (De Rosa et al., 2024). However, more than 50 Mha in the European Union have the potential to store additional soil organic carbon being also far from saturation (Breure et al., 2025), thus having the opportunity to contribute to decarbonization in the EU (Fig. 1). Pan-European modelling estimations suggested a potential SOC sequestration of 400–1300 Mt CO₂ eq. by 2050, allocating 12–28 % of the European arable land to different carbon farming activities (Lugato et al., 2014). Other study suggest shorter-term implementations having higher technical potential of 300–700 Mt CO₂ eq. per year (Zomer et al., 2017). The technical sequestration potential for EU-27 including agroforestry might be even higher, reaching 1566 Mt CO₂ eq. per year (Aertsens et al., 2013). This estimate can be further increased by taking into account soil emission reductions, especially N₂O from fertilizer in agriculture, as specifically accounted by CRCF regulation on quantification. It is worth noting that these estimates refer to technical potential that can be much lower than the realistically achievable carbon sequestration, due to various socio-economic and environmental constraints. In a recent review of scientific literature and national information, it was suggested an achievable agricultural soil carbon sequestration of 55 Mt CO₂ eq. per year in the EU (Rodrigues et al., 2021). This would generate credits up to 6 billion of Euro, if the expected price will reach 100 Euro per t of CO₂eq.

However, it has been shown that the capital required at the farm level to fund carbon farming is quite substantial (Deloitte, 2025). To mobilize the necessary capital for implementing carbon farming practices, the CRCF should facilitate and promote blended finance; the incorporation of public and philanthropic funds to mobilize private capital into markets. This includes proposing the methodologies for the various end uses of carbon units and enabling the coordinated financing of multiple stakeholders within a single farm.

With rigorous quality criteria for monitoring and reporting processes and a governance that mandates third-party verification and certification-related information in an EU-wide registry, the regulation provides a blueprint for credible quantification of emission/removals.

Moreover, the carbon farming activities are subjected to minimum sustainability requirement and should provide mandatory co-benefits for biodiversity and ecosystems. As the current carbon prices alone may be insufficient to cover the investment costs for transitioning to carbon farming practices, the full sustainability dimension of CRCF regulation can be a starting point for a broader outcome-based market that rewards land stewardship by farmers for healthy food, healthy soils, healthy ecosystems and conservation and restoration of biodiversity and clean water sources (see next section).

New business opportunities may also be facilitated by carbon farming activity to reward, not only certified units, but also new production systems. A typical example is the peatland rewetting combined with 'paludiculture', that can reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 4–5 times compared to cultivated drained peatland, produce biomass for different purposes and increase biodiversity (Tanneberger et al., 2022).

2.5. Farming beyond carbon and regenerative agriculture

Approximately 95 % of the world's food is produced from soil, highlighting the critical importance of healthy soils in ensuring global food security and agri-business competitiveness (Kopittke et al., 2019). Healthy soils underpin farm productivity through improved nutrient cycling, enhanced water-holding capacity, and greater resilience to climatic stressors.

The global food and agriculture industry shows increasing interest to support changing the farming practices across its supply-sheds to ensure reliable supply that is future-proof, meets new market demands and creates value (Kashmanian, 2017). The sustainability frameworks designed by these multi-national food and agriculture companies often follow the concept of regenerative agriculture (Giller et al., 2021; Klausner et al., 2025). Regenerative agriculture that prioritizes soil health and ecosystem services, is considered to have the potential to transform the agri-food sector and contribute to a more regenerative, climate-resilient food system (Mishra et al., 2022).

Soil carbon is often an important part of the metrics to be monitored, but these programmes often go beyond carbon including biodiversity, water quality, farmers' socio-economic aspects and animal welfare (Khangura et al., 2023; Klausner et al., 2025; Sher et al., 2024). Similarly as for carbon farming, cost-effective yet robust monitoring, reporting and verification systems are necessary to ensure accountability and transparency of private and public incentive schemes in the market (Deloitte, 2025).

Agronomic principles and practices considered to be part of regenerative agriculture are minimal soil disturbance, maximizing soil cover, increased crop diversification, integrating livestock management, reviewing nutrient management with often relying more on biological nutrient cycles and agroforestry, among others (Giller et al., 2021; Klausner et al., 2025). However, it has been emphasized that these practices should not be promoted without considering the local context and farmer needs.

Regenerative practices such as cover cropping, reduced soil disturbance, and favouring organic amendments may improve soil health and thereby enhance farmers' yield resilience against weather events, while lowering fertiliser and irrigation costs and thereby reducing external dependencies (Fig. 1). These direct benefits constitute a private value proposition for farmers. However, similar as with the carbon farming, the change of farming to this new business model, requests that farmers invest upfront in new machineries, seeding and other interventions. A study on 12 crops estimated that upfront investments to implement regenerative agriculture practices ranged from 2000 to 5000 euro ha⁻¹, with a payback period of around 9 years considering lower costs and possible increase in yields (Deloitte, 2025). Financial support, especially for the upfront investments, is a key point for success, next to local technical support that adapts the transition to local conditions.

Regenerative agriculture is still in its infancy in the European Union (EU) due to a combination of policy, economic, cultural, and structural

barriers. Many regenerative practices require upfront investments in equipment, training, and infrastructure, yet EU farmers often lack access to targeted funding and technical support to facilitate such transitions. Additionally, the EU has a higher proportion of small- to medium-sized farms compared to the United States, which limits economies of scale and makes it challenging for individual farmers to absorb the costs of adopting regenerative techniques like cover cropping, reduced tillage, or agroforestry. Historically, the EU agricultural policy has prioritized intensive farming systems, with significant support for conventional practices that rely on synthetic inputs and monocultures. Furthermore, the EU's high variability in pedo-climatic conditions across Member States, coupled with differing levels of political commitment, complicates the development of unified strategies for scaling regenerative practices. The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), the EU's primary agricultural funding mechanism, has traditionally supported direct payments to farmers rather than incentivizing compliance with sustainability targets. While recent reforms have introduced eco-schemes to reward environmentally friendly practices, these remain voluntary and underfunded. However, the EU's broader policy shift toward sustainability with many policy initiatives in the EU Green Deal could further accelerate this transition in agriculture by prioritizing soil health, biodiversity, and carbon sequestration.

2.6. Agritech solutions

The recent publication of the EC's Vision for Agriculture and Food underlines the need for digitalisation, research and innovative AgriTech solutions to revolutionise farming systems and reduce cost for better incomes to farmers (European Commission, 2025b). The establishment and operation of the 100 living labs of research and innovation within the mission "A Soil Deal for Europe" (Panagos et al., 2024a) can offer knowledge and support to farmers for better nutrient inputs, sustainable soil management and maximisation of income. The digitalisation, Artificial intelligence and innovative AgriTech technologies have a potential to revolutionise farming and reduce on-farm costs which at the end will contribute to better incomes.

Artificial Intelligence technologies have the potential to impact virtually all on-farm activities and could help accelerate the transition to precision application of inputs and targeted management of specific locations in the field. Many farms face spatial challenges in management from variation in soils and associated differences in nutrient content, pH, salinity and other factors. Existing and emerging proximal and remote sensing technologies combined with machine learning approaches are adding new insights into field-scale variation of soils and their resulting impacts on agronomic outcomes. Small and inexpensive sensors linked wirelessly and analysed with machine learning algorithms offer insights into near real-time environmental attributes and plant performance (Farooq et al., 2019). Similarly, new proximal and remote sensing technologies can augment and expand insights from traditional soil sampling allowing for more precise and efficient application of inputs. These approaches range from novel technologies sensors used to map fields (Cho et al., 2016) to drone- and satellite-based approaches using a range of spectral signals (Weiss et al., 2020).

Although such technologies have been available for many years, the accessibility of new machine learning approaches, distributed computing, and machine connectivity offer an opportunity to accelerate adoption through reduced costs and ease of use on fields. These technologies can reduce water use by over 30 % in irrigated fields (Adeyemi et al., 2018) and offer a range of new approaches in precision application of crop protection and fertiliser inputs (Bhagat et al., 2022). New machine learning approaches also show promise in carbon mapping and could lower costs while improving field sampling and monitoring, reporting, and verification of carbon removals and other soil health indicators. All these new methodologies, while extremely promising, would need to be accompanied by appropriate training to allow farmers and stakeholders to apply and take best of them.

2.7. Biofertilisers and biopesticides

The EU agriculture is highly dependent on imports of fertilisers. More than 70 % of the World's phosphate reserves are in the Moroccan sedimentary phosphate deposits (Jasinski, 2021) and the EU imports 88 % of urea from 4 countries (European Commission, 2025b). Therefore, the EU intends to reduce these excessive dependencies by investing in soil improvement products such as bio-based fertilisers and bio-stimulants, and crop protection through microbes (biopesticides). Bio-based fertilisers (BBFs) aim to reduce the European Union's (EU) dependence on imported mineral fertilisers by recycling and reusing nutrient-rich by-streams (Kurniawati et al., 2023).

In addition to traditional biofertiliser approaches such as manure, new rapidly emerging biotechnologies can increase biological nitrogen fixation in soils. These technologies often involve inoculation or application of Rhizobia and free-living bacteria to plants and soils to accelerate N fixation and increase yields (Htwe et al., 2019). The biofertiliser market, including technologies such as inoculants for nitrogen fixation, is growing at an annual rate of almost 13 % and is expected to reach a size of almost 3 billion \$US by 2030 (Size, 2024). Biostimulant technologies are also growing at a rapid pace and include a very broad range of technologies intended to improve nutrient availability to plants by stimulating nutrient turnover and plant uptake in agricultural systems. These compounds can include natural and/or synthetic compounds and are now used extensively in a range of conventional and organic agricultural systems with particularly rapid uptake in European agriculture (Ruzzi et al., 2024). These products can also strengthen plant cell walls, increase the production of their own phytohormones as a defence mechanism against pests, diseases, drought or other abiotic stress, and increase the amount of chlorophyll, thereby improving photosynthesis. Research into the effects of these compounds on soil processes and health is still at early stages, but it indicates potential to improve nutrient cycling leading to reductions in plant nutrient stress and, thus, fertilisers applications (Van Oosten et al., 2017).

Beyond the widely recognized potential effects of farming practices on carbon sequestration (Beillouin et al., 2023; Griscom et al., 2017), the commercialization of emerging technologies like bio-fertilisers and bio-stimulants may offer opportunities to close the innovation gap in the private sector (Fig. 1) and enhance agroecosystem resilience. These innovations may: i) reduce direct and indirect N₂O emissions by improving the plant's capacity to compete for N, and ii) increase the fertilizer use efficiency thus reducing the fertilizer import and their associated CO₂ cost. Bio-stimulants may also enhance plant growth and resilience contributing to increased carbon inputs to soil. However, inconsistent formulations, fragmented regulatory frameworks, and limited understanding of their mechanisms of action can be a significant barrier to their broader adoption (Khoulati et al., 2025).

The global biopesticide market is expected to grow from €4 billion in 2020 with a rate of 10–20 % per year, with the EU being a major player in this market (Marrone, 2019). In this context, in 2025, the European Commission will put forward a proposal to accelerate the access to biopesticides onto the EU market (European Commission, 2025b).

2.8. Banking and insurance sector

The private sector can finance competitiveness and invest in soil health. In many countries, farmers and landowners use their land as collateral to secure loans from banks. The financial sector (the example of Rabobank) offers specialized loan or insurance programs for farmers, which often take into account farming practices or even the quality and fertility of the soil (Deloitte, 2025; Rabobank, 2025). These programs may provide more favourable interest rates, discounts or repayment terms for farmers who use sustainable agricultural practices that promote soil health. Similar conditions may also apply in the insurance sector as healthier farms can profit from better insurance conditions. Financial products in the forms of loans or grants may offer the means to

farmers to finance the upfront investment costs necessary to make the transition towards more regenerative practices and carbon farming (Deloitte, 2025; Rabobank, 2023).

Similarly as for carbon farming and regenerative agriculture, a standardized way of reporting, monitoring and verification on sustainability in the EU food chain is needed to assure transparency and accountability (Acs et al., 2025). The Open Soil Health Assessment Framework (Bodemindex) is an example to enable farmers, agricultural organizations, and other stakeholders to assess the sustainability of their soil management practices and make data-informed decisions to optimize soil health. This, in turn, will contribute to improved crop yields, reduced environmental impact, and enhanced ecosystem services (Ros et al., 2022). The Open Soil Health Assessment Framework can be used to show the farmers contribution regarding to environmental, social benefits and societal pressure that is increasing.

2.9. Laboratories

Routine soil testing currently remains limited across agricultural, urban, and natural areas. Even in countries where cropland testing is common, it typically focuses on a narrow set of soil properties—primarily those related to soil fertility—rather than providing a comprehensive assessment of soil health (Robinson et al., 2024). The increased interest in healthy soils by the public and private sector and its emphasis on monitoring, reporting and verification (European Commission, 2024b; European Council, 2025), is expected to increase the need for reliable soil sampling, more comprehensive soil testing and interpretation tools. This increased demand is expected to have a positive impact on the business of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) as they are often operating in the sector of laboratories (European Commission, 2023).

The increased demand for cost-effective soil analyses and the need to measure novel soil properties will likely push the commercialization of innovative sampling and analytical methodologies. For example, the proposed Soil Monitoring Law will better address soil monitoring in the EU Member States by measuring at 24 properties (10 descriptors) across a large number of soil samples on a regular basis. The amendments by the Parliament went even further and propose analysis in soil properties including some that are not yet commercially routinely measured such as the contamination by pharmaceutical and veterinary products (European Parliament, 2024). While the final version still needs to be approved by the Parliament and the Council, they both reached a provisional agreement in April 2025 that includes the measurement of emerging contaminants such as PFAS and pesticides (European Council, 2025). When implemented, the increased demand for measuring emerging pollutants will push towards methodological standardization, and the commercial exploitation of methodologies and cost-effective technologies for screening and quantification (Shen et al., 2024). In addition, the growing demand of soil data to monitor the status in soils and the European Commission initiative “Test your soil for free” might push the technological advancements for commercial exploitation in alternatives for wet chemistry that are cheaper and faster, such as proximal sensing techniques such as spectroscopy (Nocita et al., 2015).

Some laboratories go beyond the delivery of raw data and provide their customers with an interpretation of the results based on decision support tools (Reijneveld, 2023). The increased interest in soil health by the public and private sector may increase the commercially available tools to interpret soil data that go beyond the traditional productivity function, and instead encompass other soil functions (e.g. soil carbon sequestration), and support diverse land uses beyond agriculture, such as natural ecosystems and urban areas.

3. Challenges

As the European Union strives to improve soil health, it is clear that the current pace of progress is insufficient to meet the pressing

challenges posed by food security, climate change, and biodiversity loss. In this section, we discuss the key challenges that need to be addressed in order to unlock the potential of healthier soils to boost competitiveness (Fig. 3).

The current progress in targeting soil health and sustainability is not sufficient to meet the challenges posed by food security, climate change, soil degradation and biodiversity loss. There is a clear need to accelerate innovation (Fig. 3) and scale up business models in soil health. Educating consumers about the importance of soil health and the benefits of sustainable agriculture is crucial for creating a market demand for products grown through environmentally friendly practices. Traditional business models in the farming sector have relied on one-to-one collaborations between individual food chain industries and farmers. However, to drive meaningful changes and promote sustainable agriculture practices, there is a growing need to scale up interactions and involve larger groups from both parties. Furthermore, a collaborative approach that leverages public-private partnerships and joint funding is essential to accelerate the transition to regenerative agriculture and foster cooperation throughout the entire value chain.

A clear, simplified, and comprehensive policy framework (Fig. 3) is essential for promoting sustainable agriculture practices and improving soil health. Such a framework should provide a coherent set of regulations and incentives that support the adoption of environmentally friendly farming methods, reduce soil degradation, and promote sustainability. Furthermore, innovators and business developers often lack clarity on the definition and measurements of soil health, which can hinder the development of effective solutions and business models. A clear understanding of what constitutes soil health, how to measure it and which indicators to be used is essential for creating impactful innovations and sustainable business models that prioritize soil health. The EC's proposal for a Soil Monitoring Law moves in that direction (European Commission, 2023).

Implementing sustainable soil management practices often requires significant upfront investments (Fig. 3). Those investments can take considerable amount of time to yield economic returns, making it challenging for stakeholders. While some practices, such as manure application, compost and biochar, may have a relatively fast impact on soil health (Agegnehu et al., 2016; Rayne and Aula, 2020), most management practices (e.g., agroforestry, organic fertilization, reduced tillage, cover crops, irrigation efficiency etc.) require a considerable amount of time (5–10 years) to show their benefits (Khangura et al., 2023; Rosati et al., 2021). This makes challenging the monitoring of progresses over time and verifying the effectiveness of farmers' efforts, which is essential for rewarding them through the supply chain

(Efthimiou, 2025; Klauser et al., 2025). In addition, the impact of management practices in regenerative agriculture becomes positive after 3–5 years. Consequently, incentives can help offset these costs and potentially reduce the payback period by half. However, currently, the EU funding available for incentives to support the transition to regenerative agriculture is limited, covering only 2–6 % of the costs.

The application of farming practices in the context of carbon farming and beyond carbon (e.g. regenerative agriculture) should ensure farmer profitability as farmers are the key actors (Fig. 3). However, profitability in all value chain is also important to be considered together with the social benefits and sustainability needs. For farmers the focus is mainly in increasing yields, reducing input costs and increase soil health in long-term for revaluation of their farm. As of the rest of the actors, profitability can be achieved by increasing carbon sequestration, increase circularity (reduce waste), ensure stable supply, improve the quality of products and meet new consumer demands.

Many soil-dependent ecosystem services (ES), notably water-quantity regulation, biodiversity corridors, and greenhouse-gas abatement, manifest at spatial scales exceeding individual farm boundaries. Effective provision, therefore, requires collective action among neighbouring land managers and alignment with catchment-scale planning authorities (Schulte et al., 2014). Business-model innovation must incorporate governance mechanisms (Fig. 3) -such as producer co-operatives, landscape service companies, or impact-investment vehicles-that can bundle, verify, and monetise aggregated service outcomes. Digital platforms for distributed ledger technologies and remote-sensing-based monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) now offer cost-efficient tools to operationalise such collective models. Additionally, the living labs and lighthouses, scattered across Europe and funded by EC's Mission "A Soil Deal for Europe" could act as drivers in this cooperative transition.

Shrinkage of land due to land take (loss of multifunctional, fertile soils and in the deterioration of biodiversity and ecosystem services), soil sealing and land grabbing (Marquard et al., 2020) is a major threat for environmental sustainability and food security. According to the European Environmental Agency (EEA), the net land take within the European Union (EU) between 2012 and 2018 averaged approximately 450 km² annually, equivalent to the land area of the Greek island of Samos. The EU has set an ambitious target of achieving 700 GW of solar photovoltaic (PV) capacity by 2030 under the REPowerEU Plan (REPowerEU Plan, 2022). To meet this goal, with an estimated 60-70 % of the required PV capacity may necessitate ground-mounted installations, which typically require approximately 2 ha per megawatt (MW) of capacity resulting in a demand of circa 1 million ha equal to 1 % of EU arable land (Chatzipanagi and Jäger-Waldau, 2023). Land allocation highlights the urgent need for integrated spatial planning and the prioritization of non-arable or marginal lands to mitigate competition between renewable energy infrastructure and agricultural production. Therefore, careful spatial planning and protection of high-quality, productive soils are important for EU food security and ecosystems preservation into account the new challenges (Fig. 3).

Scientists and researchers need to support the solutions from private sector, thus collaborating closer with SMEs and big companies (Fig. 3). Collaboration between policy makers, growers, agrifood chain, banks, scientists, researchers, advisors, land owners and private sector companies is crucial for developing and implementing effective solutions for sustainable agriculture and soil health.

There is a need for EU to invest more in the digital transformation of the agricultural sector with the use of open data and AI to develop sustainable business models (Fig. 3). Crop yield prediction, soil health management practices, pest management and food supply optimization are some examples in which the EU faces the challenge to best use AI and open data. Access to high-quality soil data is essential for scientists, policymakers, landowners, and the private sector to conduct robust research, make informed decisions, implement effective land management practices, and develop sustainable business models that prioritize

Fig. 3. Challenges in boosting EU Competitiveness with healthier soils.

soil health and sustainability. With open access data available and AI technologies, stakeholders should have options to analyse complex datasets, extract meaningful patterns, develop predictive models and improve decision making. The availability of open access data, combined with the power of AI technologies, enables stakeholders to unlock new insights and opportunities for data-driven decision making. By applying advanced analytics and machine learning techniques (neural networks, etc), stakeholders can analyze complex datasets, identify meaningful patterns, develop predictive models, and make more informed decisions that drive better environmental, social and financial outcomes.

The European Commission, through the establishment of the EU Soil Observatory (EUSO) and coordination of the largest EU soil sampling survey named LUCAS (Orgiazzi et al., 2018) generates open-access data and, has made important steps for ensure data availability and accessibility. Similar actions should be also taken by private sector and national authorities. Extensive field soil surveys and open access datasets are urgently required to address the issue of scarce soil data across Europe, which hinders effective land management and environmental protection. In many regions, national soil maps and databases rely on legacy datasets collected decades ago, often at low resolution and without accounting for new challenges such as carbon farming, soil degradation, climate change impacts, or land-use intensification. To bridge this gap, the EU has emphasized the need for harmonized, high-resolution soil monitoring systems, as outlined in the proposed Soil Monitoring Law.

4. Conclusive remarks

The Competitive Compass for the EU sets the path to become a place where future technologies, services and clean products are invented, manufactured, while being the first climate neutral continent. Soil health can play an important role in increasing EU competitiveness as clearly shown by the list of business models presented in this manuscript. Soil biodiversity may advance the production of molecules of medical interest as shown in recent findings. Bioremediation sector is expected to grow exponentially due to the application of the Soil Monitoring Law targeting remediation of contaminated sites across EU. Soil-health business models can also contribute as carbon sink to increase EU decarbonisation. The Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming may contribute to farmers income (an initial estimate is to about €1 billion per year – potentially up to €6 billion), but also boost new technologies (sensors, software development, AI) and jobs in the EU.

The adoption of digitalisation, AI, and innovative Agritech solutions has the potential to revolutionise farming systems, reduce costs, and increase incomes for farmers, while also promoting sustainable soil management and environmental sustainability. The biofertiliser and biopesticide markets are expected to grow rapidly, €3 billion by 2030 (biofertilisers) and a rate of 10–20 % per year (biopesticides), offering opportunities for the EU to reduce its dependence on external inputs and promote sustainable agriculture. Finally, the Banking sector shows an increasing interest in funding and evaluating liability and loan rates to farmers and stakeholders who invest on soil health.

Concluding, we underline that the growth of the bioremediation sector, biofertilizer and biopesticide markets, volunteer carbon farming market and the adoption of digitalization and AgriTech solutions can also drive innovation, reduce costs, and increase incomes for farmers, ultimately enhancing the EU's competitiveness and environmental sustainability, and paving the way for a more prosperous and resilient future.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

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analysis, Data curation. **Laurent Thannberger:** Writing – original draft. **Elena Kalimeri:** Writing – original draft. **Erik Mathijs:** Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Arjan Reijneveld:** Writing – original draft. **Sara Guerrini:** Conceptualization. **Pascal Chapot:** Writing – original draft. **PANAGOS PANOS:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Julian Kremers:** Writing – original draft. **Darina Štyriaková:** Writing – original draft. **Emanuele Lugato:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology. **Ramon Van Der Tol:** Writing – original draft. **Alberto Orgiazzi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Paul Martin:** Writing – original draft.

Declaration of Competing Interest

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- Abatenh, E., Gizaw, B., Tsegaye, Z., Wassie, M., 2017. The role of microorganisms in bioremediation-a review. *Open J. Environ. Biol.* 2, 038–046.
- ACS, S., Costa Leite, J., Sanyé-Mengual, E., Caivano, A., Catarino, R., Druon, J.-N., Di Marcantonio, F., De Jong, B., Guerrero, I., Gurría, P., 2025. Towards sustainable food systems: developing a monitoring framework for the EU. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 8, 1502081.
- Acton, D.F., Gregorich, L.J., 1995. Health our Soil. *Sustain. Agric. Can.*
- Adeyemi, O., Grove, I., Peets, S., Domun, Y., Norton, T., 2018. Dynamic neural network modelling of soil moisture content for predictive irrigation scheduling. *Sensors* 18, 3408.
- Aertsens, J., De Nocker, L., Gobin, A., 2013. Valuing the carbon sequestration potential for european agriculture. *Land Use Policy* 31, 584–594.
- Agegehu, G., Bass, A.M., Nelson, P.N., Bird, M.I., 2016. Benefits of biochar, compost and biochar–compost for soil quality, maize yield and greenhouse gas emissions in a tropical agricultural soil. *Sci. Total Environ.* 543, 295–306.
- Ballabio, C., Jones, A., Panagos, P., 2024. Cadmium in topsoils of the european Union—an analysis based on LUCAS topsoil database. *Sci. Total Environ.* 912, 168710.
- Ballabio, C., Panagos, P., Lugato, E., Huang, J.-H., Orgiazzi, A., Jones, A., Fernández-Ugalde, O., Borrelli, P., Montanarella, L., 2018. Copper distribution in european

- topsoils: an assessment based on LUCAS soil survey. *Sci. Total Environ.* 636, 282–298.
- Beillouin, D., Corbeels, M., Demenois, J., Berre, D., Boyer, A., Fallot, A., Feder, F., Cardinael, R., 2023. A global meta-analysis of soil organic carbon in the anthropocene. *Nat. Commun.* 14, 3700.
- Bhagat, P.R., Naz, F., Magda, R., 2022. Artificial intelligence solutions enabling sustainable agriculture: a bibliometric analysis. *PLoS One* 17, e0268989.
- Blaskovich, M.A., Cooper, M.A., 2025. Antibiotics re-booted—time to kick back against drug resistance. *npj Antimicrob. Resist.* 3, 1–20.
- Bouma, J., McBratney, A., 2013. Framing soils as an actor when dealing with wicked environmental problems. *Geoderma* 200 130–139.
- Breure, T.S., De Rosa, D., Panagos, P., Cotrufo, M.F., Jones, A., Lugato, E., 2025. Revisiting the soil carbon saturation concept to inform a risk index in European agricultural soils. *Nat. Commun.* 16, 2538.
- Brevik, E.C., Slaughter, L., Singh, B.R., Steffan, J.J., Collier, D., Barnhart, P., Pereira, P., 2020. Soil and human health: current status and future needs. *Air Soil Water Res.* 13, 1178622120934441.
- Briassoulis, D., 2023. Agricultural plastics as a potential threat to food security, health, and environment through soil pollution by microplastics: problem definition. *Sci. Total Environ.* 892, 164533.
- Bünemann, E.K., Bongiorno, G., Bai, Z., Creamer, R.E., De Deyn, G., De Goede, R., Flesskens, L., Geissen, V., Kuypers, T.W., Mäder, P., 2018. Soil quality—a critical review. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 120, 105–125.
- Chatzipanagi, A., Jäger-Waldau, A., 2023. The European solar communication—will it pave the road to achieve 1 TW of photovoltaic system capacity in the European Union by 2030? *Sustainability* 15 (8), 6531.
- Cho, Y., Sudduth, K.A., Chung, S.-O., 2016. Soil physical property estimation from soil strength and apparent electrical conductivity sensor data. *Biosyst. Eng.* 152, 68–78.
- Criscioli, I., Martelli, A., Falconi, I., Galioto, F., Lasorella, M.V., Maurino, S., Phillips, A., Bonati, G., Dara Guccione, G., 2024. Lessons learned from existing carbon removal methodologies for agricultural soils to drive European Union policies. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 75, e13577.
- De Rosa, D., Ballabio, C., Lugato, E., Fasiolo, M., Jones, A., Panagos, P., 2024. Soil organic carbon stocks in European croplands and grasslands: how much have we lost in the past decade? *Glob. Change Biol.* 30, e16992.
- Deloitte, 2025. Closing the gap: An analysis of the costs and incentives for regenerative agriculture in Europe.
- Draghi, M., 2024. The future of European competitiveness: Report by Mario Draghi. Strasbourg.
- Efthimiou, N., 2025. Governance and degradation of soil in the EU. An overview of policies with a focus on soil erosion. *Soil Tillage Res.* 245, 106308.
- EUR-lex, 2024. European Union law portal.
- European Commission, 2023. Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience.
- European Commission, 2024a. European Union priorities 2024–2029.
- European Commission, 2024b. Regulation (EU) 2024/3012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2024 establishing a Union certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products.
- European Commission, 2025a. A Competitiveness Compass for the EU. COM(2025) 30 final.
- European Commission, 2025b. A Vision for Agriculture and Food.
- European Council, 2025. Soil Monitoring Law.
- European Parliament, 2024. Soil Monitoring and Resilience.
- FAO, 2021. Assessment of agricultural plastics and their sustainability: A call for action. *Assessment of Agricultural Plastics and Their Sustainability: A Call for Action.*
- Farooq, M.S., Riaz, S., Abid, A., Abid, K., Naeem, M.A., 2019. A survey on the role of IoT in agriculture for the implementation of smart farming. *Ieee Access* 7, 156237–156271.
- Fendrich, A.N., Van Eynde, E., Stasinopoulos, D.M., Rigby, R.A., Mezquita, F.Y., Panagos, P., 2024. Modeling arsenic in European topsoils with a coupled semiparametric (GAMLSS-RF) model for censored data. *Environ. Int.* 185, 108544.
- Francucci, F., Trincardi, F., Barbanti, A., Zacchini, M., Sprovieri, M., 2020. Linking bioecology to redevelopment in contaminated sites: potentials and enabling factors. *Front. Environ. Sci.* 8, 144.
- Gavriilidou, A., Kautsar, S.A., Ziburanni, N., Krug, D., Müller, R., Medema, M.H., Ziemert, N., 2022. Compendium of specialized metabolite biosynthetic diversity encoded in bacterial genomes. *Nat. Microbiol.* 7, 726–735.
- Giller, K.E., Hijbeek, R., Andersson, J.A., Sumberg, J., 2021. Regenerative agriculture: an agronomic perspective. *Outlook Agric.* 50, 13–25.
- Griscom, B.W., Adams, J., Ellis, P.W., Houghton, R.A., Lomax, G., Miteva, D.A., Schlesinger, W.H., Shoch, D., Siikamäki, J.V., Smith, P., 2017. Natural climate solutions. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 114, 11645–11650.
- Hofmann, T., Ghoshal, S., Tufenkji, N., Adamowski, J.F., Bayen, S., Chen, Q., Demokritou, P., Flury, M., Hüffer, T., Ivleva, N.P., 2023. Plastics can be used more sustainably in agriculture. *Commun. Earth Environ.* 4, 332.
- Htwe, A.Z., Moh, S.M., Soe, K.M., Moe, K., Yamakawa, T., 2019. Effects of biofertilizer produced from bradyrhizobium and streptomyces griseoflavus on plant growth, nodulation, nitrogen fixation, nutrient uptake, and seed yield of mung bean, cowpea, and soybean. *Agronomy* 9, 77.
- Jangra, M., Travin, D.Y., Aleksandrova, E.V., Kaur, M., Darwish, L., Koteva, K., Klepacki, D., Wang, W., Tiffany, M., Sokaribo, A., 2025. A broad-spectrum lasso peptide antibiotic targeting the bacterial ribosome. *Nature* 19.
- Jasinski, S.M., 2021. Mineral commodity summaries: phosphate rock. US Geological Survey.
- Kashmanian, R.M., 2017. Building greater transparency in supply chains to advance sustainability. *Environ. Qual. Manag.* 26, 73–104.
- Khangura, R., Ferris, D., Wagg, C., Bowyer, J., 2023. Regenerative agriculture—a literature review on the practices and mechanisms used to improve soil health. *Sustainability* 15, 2338.
- Khoulati, A., Ouahhoud, S., Taibi, M., Ezrari, S., Mamri, S., Merah, O., Hakkou, A., Addi, M., Maleb, A., Saalaoui, E., 2025. Harnessing biostimulants for sustainable agriculture: innovations, challenges, and future prospects. *Discov. Agric.* 3, 56.
- Kibblewhite, M.G., Ritz, K., Swift, M.J., 2008. Soil health in agricultural systems. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* 363, 685–701.
- Klausner, D., De Candido, J., Clark, A., Leclerc, Y., Drabaek, I., Henry, Margaret, Lockwood, S., Thomson, R., Lawrence, J., Henry, Martina, 2025. Giving regenerative agriculture an agronomic perspective: a proposed framework from the food and beverage industry. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 9, 1576611.
- Kopittke, P.M., Menzies, N.W., Wang, P., McKenna, B.A., Lombi, E., 2019. Soil and the intensification of agriculture for global food security. *Environ. Int.* 132, 105078.
- Kurniawati, A., Stankovics, P., Hilmí, Y.S., Toth, G., Smol, M., Toth, Z., 2023. Understanding the future of bio-based fertilisers: the EU's policy and implementation. *Sustain. Chem. Clim. Action* 3, 100033.
- Lange, L., Connor, K.O., Arason, S., Bundgård-Jørgensen, U., Canalis, A., Carrez, D., Gallagher, J., Gotke, N., Huyghe, C., Jarry, B., 2021. Developing a sustainable and circular bio-based economy in EU: by partnering across sectors, upscaling and using new knowledge faster, and for the benefit of climate, environment & biodiversity, and people & business. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 8, 619066.
- Lewis, K., 2013. Platforms for antibiotic discovery. *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* 12, 371–387.
- Lim, M.W., Von Lau, E., Poh, P.E., 2016. A comprehensive guide of remediation technologies for oil contaminated soil—present works and future directions. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 109, 14–45.
- Lugato, E., Bampa, F., Panagos, P., Montanarella, L., Jones, A., 2014. Potential carbon sequestration of European arable soils estimated by modelling a comprehensive set of management practices. *Glob. Change Biol.* 20, 3557–3567.
- Marquard, E., Bartke, S., Gifreu i Font, J., Humer, A., Jonkman, A., Jürgenson, E., Marot, N., Poelmans, L., Repe, B., Rybski, R., Schröter-Schlaack, C., 2020. Land consumption and land take: enhancing conceptual clarity for evaluating spatial governance in the EU context. *Sustainability* 12 (19), 8269.
- Marrone, P.G., 2019. Pesticidal natural products—status and future potential. *Pest Manag. Sci.* 75, 2325–2340.
- Martin-Closas, L., Costa, J., Pelacho, A.M., 2017. Agronomic effects of biodegradable films on crop and field environment. *Soil Degradable Bioplastics a Sustain. Mod. Agric.* 67–104.
- McBratney, A., Field, D.J., Koch, A., 2014. The dimensions of soil security. *Geoderma* 213, 203–213.
- Mishra, A.K., Sinha, D.D., Grover, D., Roohi, Mishra, S., Tyagi, R., Sheoran, H.S., Sharma, S., 2022. Regenerative agriculture as climate smart solution to improve soil health and crop productivity thereby catalysing farmers' livelihood and sustainability. in: *Towards Sustainable Natural Resources: Monitoring and Managing Ecosystem Biodiversity*. Springer, pp. 295–309.
- Montanarella, L., Panagos, P., 2021. The relevance of sustainable soil management within the European Green Deal. *Land Use Policy* 100, 104950.
- Murray, C.J., Ikuta, K.S., Sharara, F., Swetschinski, L., Aguilar, G.R., Gray, A., Han, C., Bisignano, C., Rao, P., Wool, E., 2022. Global burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance in 2019: a systematic analysis. *Lancet* 399, 629–655.
- Nocita, M., Stevens, A., van Wesemael, B., Aitkenhead, M., Bachmann, M., Barthès, B., Dor, E.B., Brown, D.J., Clairotte, M., Csorba, A., 2015. Soil spectroscopy: an alternative to wet chemistry for soil monitoring. *Adv. Agron.* 132, 139–159.
- Orgiazzi, A., Ballabio, C., Panagos, P., Jones, A., Fernández-Ugalde, O., 2018. LUCAS soil, the largest expandable soil dataset for Europe: a review. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 69, 140–153.
- Ossai, I.C., Ahmed, A., Hassan, A., Hamid, F.S., 2020. Remediation of soil and water contaminated with petroleum hydrocarbon: a review. *Environ. Technol. Innov.* 17, 100526.
- Osterwalder, A., Pigneur, Y., 2010. *Business model generation: a handbook for visionaries, game changers, and challengers*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Panagos, P., Borrelli, P., Jones, A., Robinson, D.A., 2024a. A 1 billion euro mission: a soil deal for Europe. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 75, e13466.
- Panagos, P., Broothaerts, N., Ballabio, C., Orgiazzi, A., De Rosa, D., Borrelli, P., Liakos, L., Vieira, D., Van Eynde, E., Arias Navarro, C., Breure, T., Fendrich, A., Königinger, J., Labouyrie, M., Matthews, F., Muntwyler, A., Jimenez, J.M., Wojda, P., Yunta, F., Marechal, A., Sala, S., Jones, A., 2024b. How the EU soil observatory is providing solid science for healthy soils. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 75, e13507. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13507>.
- Panagos, P., Jones, A., Lugato, E., Ballabio, C., 2025. A soil monitoring law for Europe. *Glob. Chall.* 9, 2400336.
- Panagos, P., Van Liedekerke, M., Yigini, Y., Montanarella, L., 2013. Contaminated sites in Europe: review of the current situation based on data collected through a European network. *J. Environ. Public Health* 2013.
- Pande, Veni, Pandey, S.C., Sati, D., Pande, Veena, Samant, M., 2020. Bioremediation: an emerging effective approach towards environment restoration. *Environ. Sustain.* 3, 91–103.
- Prasad, M.N.V., de Jesus Alves, L., Nunes, F.C., 2021. Global remediation industry and trends. *Handb. Assist. Amend. Enhanc. Sustain. Remediat. Technol.* 1–28.
- Rabobank, 2023. Sustainability - Accelerate productive & regenerative agriculture.
- Rabobank, 2025. The Open Soil Index makes sustainability concret.
- Ramírez-Rendon, D., Passari, A.K., Ruiz-Villafán, B., Rodríguez-Sanoja, R., Sánchez, S., Demain, A.L., 2022. Impact of novel microbial secondary metabolites on the pharma industry. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 106, 1855–1878.
- Rayne, N., Aula, L., 2020. Livestock manure and the impacts on soil health: a review. *Soil Syst.* 4, 64.

- Reijneveld, J.A., 2023. Soil carbon check: a tool for monitoring and guiding soil carbon sequestration. *Front. Agric. Sci. Eng.* 10, 248–261. <https://doi.org/10.15302/J-FASE-2023499>.
- Robinson, D.A., Bentley, L., Jones, L., Feeney, C., Garbutt, A., Tandy, S., Lebron, I., Thomas, A., Reinsch, S., Norton, L., 2024. Five decades' experience of long-term soil monitoring, and key design principles, to assist the EU soil health mission. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 75, e13570.
- Rodrigues, L., Hardy, B., Huyghebeart, B., Fohrafellner, J., Fornara, D., Barancíková, G., Bárcena, T.G., De Boever, M., Di Bene, C., Feizienė, D., 2021. Achievable agricultural soil carbon sequestration across Europe from country-specific estimates. *Glob. Change Biol.* 27, 6363–6380.
- Ros, G.H., Verweij, S.E., Janssen, S.J., De Haan, J., Fujita, Y., 2022. An open soil health assessment framework facilitating sustainable soil management. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 56, 17375–17384.
- Rosati, A., Borek, R., Canali, S., 2021. Agroforestry and organic agriculture. *Agrofor. Syst.* 95, 805–821.
- Ruzzi, M., Colla, G., Roupheal, Y., 2024. Biostimulants in agriculture II: towards a sustainable future, frontiers in plant science. *Frontiers Media SA*.
- Sa'adu, I., Farsang, A., 2023. Plastic contamination in agricultural soils: a review. *Environ. Sci. Eur.* 35, 13.
- Scarascia-Mugnozza, G., Sica, C., Russo, G., 2011. Plastic materials in european agriculture: actual use and perspectives. *J. Agric. Eng.* 42, 15–28.
- Schulte, R.P., Creamer, R.E., Donnellan, T., Farrelly, N., Fealy, R., O'Donoghue, C., O'hUallachain, D., 2014. Functional land management: a framework for managing soil-based ecosystem services for the sustainable intensification of agriculture. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 38, 45–58.
- Shen, Y., Wang, L., Ding, Y., Liu, S., Li, Y., Zhou, Z., Liang, Y., 2024. Trends in the analysis and exploration of per-and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in environmental matrices: a review. *Crit. Rev. Anal. Chem.* 54, 3171–3195.
- Sher, A., Li, H., Hamid, Y., Nasir, B., Zhang, J., 2024. Importance of regenerative agriculture: climate, soil health, biodiversity and its socioecological impact. *Discov. Sustain.* 5, 1–23.
- Sible, C.N., Seebauer, J.R., Below, F.E., 2021. Plant biostimulants: a categorical review, their implications for row crop production, and relation to soil health indicators. *Agronomy* 11, 1297.
- Size, B.M., 2024. Share & Trends Analysis Report by Product (Nitrogen Fixing, Phosphate Solubilizing), by Application (Seed Treatment, Soil Treatment), and Segment Forecasts, 2012–2022.
- Tanneberger, F., Birr, F., Couwenberg, J., Kaiser, M., Luthardt, V., Nerger, M., Pfister, S., Oppermann, R., Zeitz, J., Beyer, C., 2022. Saving soil carbon, greenhouse gas emissions, biodiversity and the economy: paludiculture as sustainable land use option in German fen peatlands. *Reg. Environ. Change* 22, 69.
- Tofanelli, M.B., Wortman, S.E., 2020. Benchmarking the agronomic performance of biodegradable mulches against polyethylene mulch film: A meta-analysis. *Agronomy* 10 (10), 1618.
- Van Eynde, E., Fendrich, A.N., Ballabio, C., Panagos, P., 2023. Spatial assessment of topsoil zinc concentrations in Europe. *Sci. Total Environ.* 892, 164512.
- Van Oosten, M.J., Pepe, O., De Pascale, S., Silletti, S., Maggio, A., 2017. The role of biostimulants and bioeffectors as alleviators of abiotic stress in crop plants. *Chem. Biol. Technol. Agric.* 4, 1–12.
- Weiss, M., Jacob, F., Duveiller, G., 2020. Remote sensing for agricultural applications: a meta-review. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 236, 111402.
- Wouters, O.J., McKee, M., Luyten, J., 2020. Estimated research and development investment needed to bring a new Medicine to market, 2009-2018. *Jama* 323, 844–853.
- Zomer, R.J., Bossio, D.A., Sommer, R., Verchot, L.V., 2017. Global sequestration potential of increased organic carbon in cropland soils. *Sci. Rep.* 7, 15554.
- REPowerEU Plan, 2022. Communication from the European Commission COM(2022) 230 final. Available at: https://commission.europa.eu/topics/energy/repowereu_en.